

Evaluation of Bacterial Pathogens Associated with Diabetic and Non Diabetic Ulcer and The Antibiogram Among Patients of Federal Teaching Hospital (FTH), Owerri

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Abstract

Diabetic and non diabetic ulcers are among the common wounds and cause of amputation among patients. This study aims at evaluating the bacterial pathogens associated with diabetic and non diabetics ulcers and the antibiogram among patients. 385 subjects were enrolled in this study. Wound swab samples were collected from 200 diabetic patients and 185 non diabetic patients of age range 18-80 years, both male and female. The swabs collected were inoculated onto freshly prepared Blood agar and MacConkey agar plate and incubated for 24hrs at 37° C using standard bacteriological methods. All the cultured samples produced 345 isolate. Gram staining was done and to further identify the organism, biochemical test was also done. Antimicrobial susceptibility test was performed using the modified Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method on Nutrient agar according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standard Institute. The bacterial profiling of 345 isolates revealed the presence of Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria. *Staphylococcus aureus* (56.0%), *Escherichia coli* (35.1%), *Pseudomonas aerogenosa* (34.0%), *Streptococcus pyogenes* (26.75%), *Klebsiella pneumonia* (15.4%), *Proteus mirabilis* (15.4%), and *Bacillus anthracis* (17.19%). The rates of occurrence of these organisms were also statistically significant. The antibiogram revealed varying resistance patterns among the isolates. Most of the isolates from Diabetic foot ulcer patients and non diabetic foot ulcer patients were sensitive to Ciprofloxacin, Azithromycin, Ofloxacin and Peflacin while majority of the isolates were resistant to Gentamycin, Streptomycin, Cefazidime, Ceftriazone and Cefuroxime. The most sensitive bacteria isolated were *Staphylococcus aureus* followed by *Escherichia coli* while the most resistant were *Pseudomonas aerogenosa* and *Klebsiella pneumonia*. The obtained antibiotic susceptibility assay data in the present studies suggest that there is need for the discovery of newer drugs to alleviate antibiotic resistance.

Keywords: Bacterial Pathogens, Diabetic, Non Diabetic Ulcer, Antibiogra, Owerri.

Introduction

In general, foot ulcers are open wounds or sores that are frequently infected and do not heal adequately. He continues by saying that in those without diabetes, they frequently arise from a number of causes, including inadequate foot wear, poor blood circulation, or excessive strain on the feet. To preserve general foot health, it is critical to understand the dangers of non-diabetic foot ulcers and how to prevent them. For non-diabetic foot ulcers to heal successfully and avoid complications, early diagnosis and treatment are essential. The moist, warm, and nutrient-rich environment that wounds provide makes them ideal for microbial colonization, proliferation, and infection. Wounds are a significant component of the standard care that medical professionals provide to the general public. Effective wound management, particularly for chronic wounds, in a medical environment has been shown to improve function and quality of life while lowering morbidity and influencing population health [1].

Patients' presentations of foot ulcers differ depending on the situation. Human skin, the nasopharynx, the gastrointestinal tract, and other bodily areas are home to a variety of bacterial species. These bacteria are referred to be normal flora since

they have little to no ability to cause illness in the aforementioned circumstances. The first line of defense is found within the body, where the natural bacterial flora is found and friendly to every portion of the body. The skin serves as a favorable environment for the growth of pathogenic microorganisms. This increases the likelihood that a skin wound may become infected and hinders the healing process. The wounds can have a variety of causes, including acute wounds from surgery (such as surgical site infections), post-traumatic wounds (such as wounds from an accident or injury), or chronic wounds like those brought on by diabetes mellitus (such as diabetic foot) and sickle ulcer disease [2]. Notwithstanding the aforementioned, every cut or break in the skin's surface, whether from trauma, an accident, surgery, or a burn, creates an opportunity for bacterial infection. Trauma is the most frequent underlying cause of all wounds [3].

In actuality, trauma can be purposefully caused or unintentionally caused. Hospital-acquired wounds are one type of purposefully caused trauma that can be categorized based on how they were obtained. Intravenous medical devices and medically acquired or caused trauma are the most prevalent [4]. The most prevalent type of hospital-acquired wounds that are not purposefully caused are pressure sores. Bacteria belonging to the skin's saprophytic microflora are present in all wounds, albeit the kind and caliber of these germs differ depending on the wound. Because they have an impact on wound colonization and infection, some crucial aspects such the wound's origin, body location, size, and length should be considered when managing it.

If ulcers present in the leg have no tendency to heal even after 6 weeks of appropriate treatment or are still not fully healed at 12 months, it is then called chronic leg ulcer [5].

The presence of the ulcer carries a negative physical, psychological and financial impact on the patient's quality of life. Wound infections development depend on the following: the integrity and protective function of the skin, the number and types of organism and their synergy, the pathogenicity and virulence of the bacteria species, nature of surgery, use of antibiotics, and the immune-competency of the host and it is determined by presence of clinical signs as erythema, pain, tenderness, heat, oedema, cellulites and abscess/pus. They also state that, wound Infections are characterized by high bacteria burden, chronic inflammation, and unbalanced cellular defense mechanism. The most common wound pathogens include bacteria, fungi, protozoa, and viruses. Bacterial pathogens associated with wound infection include: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Streptococcus* species, *Proteus* species, and *Enterococcus* species [6].

Diabetic foot ulcer infection is essentially of many poly-microbial complications of DFUs. These are caused by bacterial infections and can be minimized by paying due attention to, identification and control of the infections. It is necessary to detect the specific pathogens and their susceptibility pattern to initiate early treatment with the appropriate antibiotics. Wound has the potential to become contaminated. Even though microorganisms cause wound infection, there is still substantial controversy about the particular mechanisms by which they do so, as well as their function in non healing injuries; because these wounds show no indication of infection. They also note that infection can occur when bacteria begin to proliferate and attach to the wound site without causing tissue damages. The wound healing process is not hindered solely by colonization and in some cases colonization might speed up the healing process [7].

This can happen when the number of bacteria in the environment substantially overwhelmed the immune system of the host. Several medical records have shown that, every year millions of people both in the urban and rural areas experience burns of different degrees and forms. Some suffer from non healing wounds, while others have acute wounds that become complicated by infections, dehiscence, or problematic scarring; as a result, are in dear need for healing. Wound treatment requires carefully considered interventions either through multiple clinic or hospital visits or the resulting costs of wound care. Each of this choice is staggering and the result cannot be guaranteed in addition to the cost effects which include: dressing materials and transport fare which most often is not easy for the out patients to meet up with [8].

In developing countries, like Nigeria, wound infections are major health problems. Records show that a huge number of people die daily of preventable and curable wound infections. Others attribute the wounds to diabolic attacks by their enemies. No matter the level, wounds are serious problems in hospitals especially in surgical practices, where clean operations can become contaminated with virulent organisms and subsequently infect the patient. The level of self medication and medical quackery among the under developed nations have confirmed that antibiotics can be purchased without expert prescription. This automatically results to abuse or misuse of antibiotics by the inquisitive public whose interest is to obtain healing thus, contributing to the emergence and spread of antimicrobial resistant pathogens. It is on record that advance infection control and management cannot completely eradicate the problems associated with wound infections, because of the high prevalence of drug resistance pathogens [9].

Furthermore, the widespread and prolonged use of antibiotics lead to the emergence of bacteria pathogens resistance in wound infections. These unequivocally contribute to high morbidity and mortality rates. It is obvious to note, that antibiotics resistant pathogens are acquired from the following: health care setting environment, health care personnel, and inpatients. In addition, Hospital acquired infections are further complicated by increasing prevalence of multi-bacteria pathogens resistant to drugs like methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA), methicillin-resistant coagulase negative

Staphylococcus (CoNS), vancomycin resistant *Enterococcus* (VRE), and poly-microbial flora and fungi. wide spread of antibiotic resistance and increase in infections caused by methicilin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and poly-microbial flora, controlling wound infections has become more difficult [10].

Never the less, wound infection is a major concern among healthcare practitioners, not only in terms of increased trauma to the patient but also in view of its burden on financial resources and the increasing requirement for cost-effective management within the healthcare system. The evaluation of bacteria pathogens associated with these wounds, be they diabetic or non diabetic especially in foot ulcer and the discovery of the antibiogram among patients will help in a lot of way in the healing processes of the patients. Hence this is the challenge of thcis research. Because, earlier research and researchers have revealed knowledge of a number of causative agents of wound infection and these have proved to be helpful in the selection of empirical therapy, on infection control measures in health institution, and in formulating rationales of antibiotic policy. As a researcher in Medical Laboratory Science, it is therefore important to identify antimicrobial drug susceptibility and resistant pathogens from both inpatient and outpatient isolates. Gather information on bacteria pathogens from diabetic and non-diabetic foot ulcer patients both inpatient and outpatient in Nigeria especially in Federal Teaching Hospital (FTH) Owerri thus, evaluating the bacteria etiologies and antimicrobial susceptibility patterns and to compare the antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of inpatients and outpatients of diabetic and non-diabetic foot ulcer from wound swab culture [11].

Non healing foot ulcer in both diabetic and non-diabetic is mainly due to several factors such as neuropathy, high plantar pressures, vascular insufficiency, reduced blood supply and neutrophil function. Non-diabetics foot ulcers typically develop due to poor circulation, prolonged pressure, or trauma to the foot. Some common causes include: peripheral artery disease (PAD). Venous insufficiency: A problem with the valve in the veins that prevents proper circulation, Neuropathy: Never damage that leads to a loss of sensation. Prolonged pressure: Pressure on the foot caused by improper footwear or extended periods of standing. The main challenge is the increased vulnerability to different potential pathogens with potentially serious outcome such as infections, gangrene, osteomyelitis, amputations and even death [12].

The risk factors and preventing or controlling them is very important. Such risk factors include: Obesity: Excess body weight can put added pressure on the feet thereby increasing the likely hood of ulcers. Smoking: this is a leading cause of PAD, which can result in inadequate blood flow to the feet. Poor footwear: Ill- fitting shoes can cause pressure points or rubbing that damages the skin. Age: elderly individuals are more susceptible to ulcers as skin becomes thinner and less elastic with age. Immobility: A sedentary life style can lead to circulatory issues making ulcers more likely [13].

An accurate diagnosis is essential to avoid inappropriate treatment that may cause deterioration of wound, delay in wound healing or harm to the patient. Hence knowing the etiology of the chronic leg ulcers becomes an important pivot for research in managing wounds and increases the quality of the life along with reduction of the financial burden [14].

The early diagnosis of infected foot ulcer and appropriate treatment based on the identification of the pathogenic organisms and their antibiogram is important for proper prognosis. Therefore, in this study, bacteria profiling in the collected swab samples of DFU and non-DFU patients was performed. The obtained isolates were also subjected to antibiotic susceptibility testing which will help provide antibiotic needed for the treatment of the ulcer. Providing an effective antimicrobial therapy is an important component in treating these infections. The presence of the ulcer carries a negative physical, psychological and financial impact on the patient's quality of life. Wound infections are one of the commonest infections that keep patients long in the hospital, since there is no proper cure for diabetes and its complications and increasing of antibiotic resistance. Most foot ulcers are not supposed to be infected if not for patient's carelessness. Patients should encourage to avoid the use of things like grated kola nut, leaves of different plants, shea butter, kerosene, bleached red oil, palm kernel oil, native chalk and putting the wound over the flame of fire. It was observed that such thing encourages microbial growth.

Materials And Methods

Study area

The Federal Teaching Hospital (FTH) Owerri served as the site for this research.

Study Population

The study population consists of 385 subjects out of which 200 were diabetic patients and 185 were non-diabetic foot ulcer patients attending Fderal Teaching Hospital (FTH) Owerri. Participants were recruited accoding to inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Ethical approval

An ethical approval letter was obtained from the hospital for sample collection from the study participants.

Statistical Analysis

Results obtained from this study, were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21.0. Results were presented in tables and percentages.

Selection Criteria

Inclusion Criteria

- 1) Only diabetic and non-diabetic patient with foot ulcers which were not healing and have lasted for over 4 weeks will be recruited as subject for the study.
- 2) Men and women of age group 18-80.
- 3) Patient with good glycemic control and Neuropathic ulcer.
- 4) Patients who are not currently on antibiotics.

Exclusion Criteria:

Patient with wound that were not up to 4weeks and surgical wounds were excluded from the study. Deep Venous Thrombosis, Malignancy, Varicose veins and traumatic ulcer were excluded.

Sample Collection

Written and oral informed consent was obtained from the patients before sample collection. The nurses in the ward and in the dressing, room helped in the sample collection. A total number of 385 samples were collected, 200 from diabetic patients and 185 from non-diabetic patients aseptically using sterile swab sticks. Swabbing was done on slough, pus or inflamed tissue areas as bacteria tend to be present in greater number in that part. Both male and female patients (in patient and out patients) with foot ulcers, their samples were collected by rotating the sterile cotton swab stick over the wound and swab stick was inserted into the transport tube containing saline and was labeled appropriately. The photograph of some of the wound sites were taken hence this is an evidence based research.

Methods

Media and Reagents:

The media used were Blood agar, MacConkey agar, Chocolate agar and Nutrient agar.

All the media used were prepared according to manufacturer's specifications as it's indicated on the media containers. The dissolved agar was autoclaved for 15mins at 121°C and dispensed aseptically into sterile Petri dishes.

Isolation methods:

All specimens collected were inoculated to freshly prepared media such as a Blood agar, MacConkey agar and Chocolate agar, streaked and incubated over night at 37°C for 24hrs. After incubation, the bacterial colonies were isolated and purified by sub-culturing onto freshly prepared Nutrient agar using a streak plate technique. After the isolates were purified, they were subjected to microscopic and colonial identification.

Microscopic and colonial identification

Characterization and identification of the bacterial isolates were achieved by initial morphological examination of the colonies in the plate (macroscopically) for colonial appearance, colour, consistency, size, odour, elevation, opacity, edge, form, haemolysis and pigmentation. Hence the results and observation were recorded.

The isolates were characterized and identified based on their cultural characteristics, Gram stain and biochemical reaction such as catalase, coagulase, oxidase, indole production test, motility and urease were done for further identification.

Gram Staining

Gram staining reaction was used to identify and differentiate pathogens in the specimen and culture by their Gram reaction (Gram positive or Gram negative) and morphology.

Gram positive organism: Stained dark purple with crystal violet and are decolorized by acetone.

Gram negative organism: Stained red because after being stained with crystal violet they are decolorized by acetone and they take up the counter stain which is neutral red.

Isolation Criteria

Organisms that have golden yellow pigment from blood agar plate that were Gram -positive cocci, coagulase-positive, motility-negative, Indole-negative and Oxidase-negative were taken to be *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Bright pink lactose fermenter colonies on MaConkey plates that were Gram-negative straight rods in pairs or singles, Indole-positive, Motility-positive, Catalase-negative, and oxidase-negative were taken to be *Escherichia coli*.

Large smooth mousy smell colonies on MacConkey agar, Gram-positive short rods in pairs or singles that are Catalase-positive, Motility-Positive, Indole-negative, Coagulase-negative and Oxidase-positive were taken as *Bacillus* spp.

Blue-green colour with fruity odour on nutrient agar. Gram negative rods, Oxidase-positive, Catalase-positive, Motility-positive and Indole negative and coagulase-negative were taken to be *Pseudomonas* spp.

Circular done-shaped, mucoid, grayish-white colonies on blood agar, Gram -negative short plump straight rods in singles or pairs, that were Indole-negative, Catalase-positive, Motility-negative, were said to be *Klebsiella* spp.

Foul smelling colorless and non lactose fermenters colonies on chocolate agar, that is Gram-negative rods in pairs or singles, Catalase-positive, Motility-positive, Indole-negative, Coagulase -negative and Oxidase-positive were said to be *Proteus* spp.

White or grayish round with smooth and glistening edge and lysis in blood agar Cocci in pairs or chains, motility-negative, coagulase-negative, Oxidase-negative, Indole-negative, Catalase-negative, and Urease-negative is said to be *Streptococcus*.

Biochemical Test Used in the Identification of the Isolate

Coagulase Test

This is used to identify *Staphylococcus aureus* which produce the enzyme coagulase. Coagulase causes plasma to clot by converting fibrinogen to fibrin. Two types of coagulases are produced by most strain of *Staphylococcus aureus*: a free coagulase which converts fibrinogen to fibrin by activating coagulase-reacting factor present in the plasma. Free cogulase is detected by clotting in the tube test.

Bound coagulase (clumping factor) which convert fibrinogen directly to fibrin without requiring a couagulase reacting factor. It can be detected by clumping of bacterial cells in the rapid slide test method. It detects the bound coagulase. For the purpose of the research, I adopted the slide test method.

Catalase Test:

This test is used to differentiate those bacteria that produce the enzyme catalase, such as *staphylococci*, from non-catalase producing bacteria such as *streptococci*.

Principle:

Catalase acts as catalyst in the breakdown of hydrogen peroxide to oxygen and water. An organism is tested for catalase production by bringing it into contact with hydrogen peroxide. Bubbles of oxygen are released if the organism is a catalase producer.

Note: The culture should not be more than 24 hours old.

Motility Test:

Principle: to determine the motility of bacterium and to differentiate between motile and non motile bacteria. Motility is the ability of an organism to move by itself by means of propeller-like flagella unique to bacteria or special fibrils that produce a gliding form of motility.

Indole Test

This is important for the identification of entrobacteriaceae examples includes *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella* spp, *Klebsiella Pneumonia*, *Provendencia* spp., break down the amino acid tryptophan with the release of Indole.

Principle

The test organism was cultured in a medium which contains tryptophan. Indole production is detected by Kovac's reagent which contains 4(p)-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde. This reacts with the indole to produce a red colored compound.

Urease Test:

This is used to differentiate organism based on their ability to hydrolyze urea with the enzyme urease. It is also used as part of the identification of several genera and species of enterobacteriaceae including *Proteus*, *Klebsiella*, some *Yersinia* and *Citrobacter* spp, as well as some *Corynebacterium* spp.

Media: Media used is Christensen's urea agar.

Media preparation: All the media were prepared strictly according to manufacturer's instruction.

Principle

The test organism was cultured in a medium which contains urea and the indicator phenol red. When the strain is urease-producing, the enzyme will break down the urea (by hydrolysis) to give ammonia and carbon dioxide. With the release of ammonia, the medium becomes alkaline as shown by change in colour of the indicator to pink-red

Oxidase test

The oxidase is used to assist in the identification of *Pseudomonas*, *Neisseria*, *Vibrio*, *Brucella* and *Pasteurella* species, all of which produce the enzyme cytochrome oxidase

Principle

A piece of filter paper is soaked with a few drops of oxidase reagent, colony of the test organism is then smeared on the filter paper. Alternatively, an oxidase reagent strip can be used. When the organism is oxidase-producing, the phenylenediamine in the reagent will be oxidized to a deep purple colour.

Material: freshly prepared oxidase reagent which was prepared according to manufacturer's instruction.

Antibiotic Susceptibility Testing

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was performed with pure colonies of culture using disc diffusion method on Nutrient agar and blood agar. Antibiotic discs were placed on the dried surface of the agar and the plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours as recommended by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI). The isolates were tested against Gram-positive and Gram-negative disc which contain the following drugs Ofloxacin (10mcg), Augmentin(30mcg), Peflacin (10mcg), Ceftazidime (30mcg), Gentamycin (10mcg), Ciprofloxacin (10mcg), Ceporex (10mcg), Ceftriaxone (30mcg), Streptomycin (30mcg), Cefuroxime (30mcg), Rifampicin (20mcg), Azithromycin (10mcg), Amoxil (20mcg), Erythromycin (20mcg), Levofloxacin (20mcg).

The zones of inhibition were measured and compared with the guidelines.

RESULTS

Table4.1: COLONIAL CHARACTERISTICS OF BACTERIAL ISOLATES

Colonial Morphological	Gram Reaction	Microscopic Appearance	Probable organism
Flat circular golden yellow pigment on Blood agar	+ve	Cocci in cluster or grape-like bunches	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
Bright pink Lactose fermenters on MacConkey	-ve	Straight rods in singles or pairs	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
Foul smelling colorless Non lactose fermenters Colonies on chocolate agar	-ve	Rods in pairs and singles	<i>Proteus spp.</i>
Blue green colour with fruity odour on nutrient agar	-ve	Short rods in singles	<i>Pseudomonas spp.</i>
Circular dome-shaped mucoid grayish white colonies on Blood Agar	-ve	Short plump straight rods in pairs or singles	<i>Klebsiella spp.</i>
White or grayish round with smooth and glistening edge and lysis in blood agar	+ve	Cocci in pairs or chains	<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>
Large smooth mousy smell colony on MacConkey	+ve	Short rods in single or pairs	<i>Bacillus anthracis</i>

Key

+ve = indicates positive

-ve = indicates negative

Table 4:2 BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF BACTERIAL ISOLATES

Organism	Catalase	Coagulase	Motility	Urease	Indole	oxidase
<i>Staphylococcus Aureus</i>	+ve	+ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	+ve	-ve	+ve	-ve	+ve	-ve
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	+ve	-ve	+ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
<i>Pseudomonas spp.</i>	+ve	-ve	+ve	-ve	-ve	+ve
<i>Klebsiella spp.</i>	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	+ve
<i>Streptococcus Pyogenes</i>	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
<i>Bacillus spp.</i>	+ve	-ve	+ve	-ve	-ve	+ve

Key:

-ve Indicates Negative

+ve Indicates positive

Table 4.3 PERCENTAGE OCCURRENCE OF THE ISOLATES

		Diabetic		Non Diabetic	
		M	F	M	F
S. aureus	88(25.5%)	26(29.5%)	17 (19.3%)	21(23.8%)	24(27.2%)
E. coli	66 (19.1%)	20(30.3%)	15(22.7%)	14(21.2%)	17(25.7%)
P. aeruginosa	64 (18.55%)	15(23.4%)	19(29.6%)	11(17.1%)	19(23.4%)
K. pneumonia	29(8.4%)	7(24.0%)	7(24.0%)	8(27.5%)	7(24.0%)
P. mirabilis	29 (8.4%)	9(31.0%)	5(24.0%)	7(24.0%)	8(27.5%)
S. pyogenes	42 (12.1%)	14(33.3%)	8(19.0%)	9(21.4%)	11(26.0%)
B. anthracis	27(7.8%)	7(25.9%)	10(37.0%)	5(18.5%)	5(18.5%)
Total	345(100)	98%	81%	75%	91%

Table 4.4a: AGE AND GENDER DISTRIBUTION

Age Group Range)	Diabetic			Non diabetic group		
	M	F	Total	M	F	Total
18-30	15	11	26	10	15	25
31-40	18	10	28	16	23	39
41-50	17	20	37	15	13	28
51-60	25	30	55	20	18	38
61-70	18	13	31	11	21	32
71-80	14	9	23	13	10	23

Table 4.4b AGE AND GENDER DISTRIBUTION IN PERCENTAGE

Age (Group Range)	Diabetic group		non diabetic group	
	M %	F %	M %	F %
18-30	15 (14.0%)	11 (11.8%)	10 (11.7%)	15 (15.0%)
31-40	18 (16.8%)	10 (10.7%)	16 (18.8%)	23 (23.0%)
41-50	17 (15.9%)	20 (21.5%)	15 (17.6%)	13 (13.0)
51-60	25 (23.3%)	30 (32.2%)	20 (23.5%)	18 (18.0%)
61-70	18 (16.8%)	13(13.9%)	11 (12.9%)	21 (21.0)
71-80	14 (13.0%)	9 (9.7%)	13 (15.2%)	10 (10%)
Total	107 (99.8%)	93 (99.8)	85 (99.7%)	100 (100%)
Grand total	385			

Table 4.5a SPECIFIC SITE OF ISOLATION

Age (Years)	DIABETIC MALE						
	P. aeruginosa	P. mirabilis	E. coli	K. pneumonia	S. aureus	S. pyogenes	B. anthracis
18-30	+	-	+	-	+	+	+
31-40	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
41-50	-	+	+	-	+	+	+
51-60	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
61-70	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
71-80	-	+	+	+	-	+	+

Key

- +: indicates that the organism was found in that age group for diabatic male subject.
- : indicates that the organism was not found in that age group for diabatic male subject.

**Table 4.5b: SPECIFIC SITE OF ISOLATION
NON-DIABETIC MALE**

Age (Years)	P.	P.	E.	K.	S.	S.	B.
	<i>aeruginosa</i>	<i>mirabilis</i>	<i>coli</i>	<i>pneumonia</i>	<i>aureus</i>	<i>pyogenes</i>	<i>anthracis</i>
18-30	+	+	+	-	+	+	-
31-40	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
41-50	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
51-60	-	+	+	+	+	+	-
61-70	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
71-80	+	+	+	-	+	+	+

Key

- +: indicates that the organism was found in that age group for diabatic male subject.
- : indicates that the organism was not found in that age group for diabatic male sub

**Table 4.5c SPECIFIC SITE OF ISOLATION
DIABETIC FEMALE**

	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>P. mirabilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumonia</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pyogenes</i>	<i>B. anthracis</i>
Age (Group Range)							
18-30	+	+	+	-	+	-	-
31-40	+	-	+	+	+	-	+
41-50	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
51-60	+	+	+	-	+	+	-
61-70	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
71-80	+	+	+	-	+	+	+

Key

+: indicates that the organism was found in that age group for diabetic male subject.

-: indicates that the organism was not found in that age group for diabetic male subject.

**Table 4.5d: SPECIFIC SITE OF ISOLATION
NON- DIABETIC FEMALE**

	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>P. mirabilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumonia</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pyogenes</i>	<i>B. anthracis</i>
Age (Group Range)							
18-30	+	-	+	+	+	+	-
31-40	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
41-50	+	+	-	+	-	+	+
51-60	-	+	+	-	+	+	-
61-70	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
71-80	+	+	-	+	+	+	-

Key

+: indicates that the organism was found in that age group for diabetic male subject.

-: indicates that the organism was not found in that age group for diabetic male subject.

Table 4.6a: Distribution of Isolates according to age range for diabetic male subjects

		Number of Isolates							NBG
		<i>P. Aeruginosa</i>	<i>P. mirabilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumonia</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pyogenes</i>	<i>B. anthracis</i>	
Age (Group Range)	No. of Subjects Examined								
18-30	15	3	0	4	0	5	1	2	3
31-40	18	5	3	2	1	4	2	1	2
41-50	17	0	1	3	0	5	3	2	3
51-60	25	4	0	5	3	7	3	1	2
61-70	18	3	3	3	2	5	2	0	1
71-80	14	0	2	3	1	0	3	1	3
Total	107	15	9	20	7	26	14	7	T=13

Total no of isolates 98

Polymicrobial 11

Key

NBG=No bacteria growth

T=Total

Table 4.6b: Distribution of Isolates according to age Range for non-diabetic male subjects

		Number of Isolates							NBG
		<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>P. mirabilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumonia</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pyogenes</i>	<i>B. anthracis</i>	
Age (Group Range)	No. of Subjects Examined								
18-30	10	1	3	1	0	4	2	0	1
31-40	16	4	2	0	1	3	2	1	3
41-50	15	2	3	0	2	3	1	2	2
51-60	20	0	3	2	3	7	3	0	3
61-70	11	2	1	3	2	1	0	1	1
71-80	13	3	2	1	0	3	2	1	2
Total	85	11	14	7	8	21	9	5	T=12

Table 4.6c: Distribution of Isolates according to age range for diabetic female subjects

		Number of Isolates							
		<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>P. mirabilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pyogenes</i>	<i>B. anthracis</i>	NBG
Age (Group range)	NO. of subjects Examined								
18-30	11	3	1	2	0	5	0	0	1
31-40	10	2	0	3	2	2	0	1	1
41-50	20	7	1	5	1	3	2	1	3
51-60	30	7	2	4	1	6	1	0	2
61-70	13	0	1	0	2	0	3	2	7
71-80	9	0	0	1	1	1	2	0	4
Total	93	19	5	15	7	17	8	4	T=18

Total no of isolates 85

Poly microbial 7

Key

NBG= No bacteria growth

T= Total

Table 4. 6d: Distribution of Isolates according to age range for non-diabetic female subjects

		Number of Isolates							
		<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>P. mirabilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pyogenes</i>	<i>B. anthracis</i>	NBG
Age (Group Range)	No. of Subjects Examined								
18-30	15	3	0	5	1	3	2	0	1
31-40	23	5	2	3	2	7	0	2	3
41-50	13	7	1	0	2	0	3	1	2
51-60	18	0	3	2	0	7	2	0	3
61-70	21	4	0	7	1	3	3	2	1
71-80	10	0	2	0	1	4	1	0	2
Total	100	19	8	17	7	24	11	5	T=12

Total isolates 82

Key

NBG= No bacteria

T=Total

Table 4.7a: Antibiotics susceptibility pattern of the aerobic Gram-negative bacteria isolates for diabetic male group

Organism No. of isolate											
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> tested											
AGE (Group range)	GRAM NEGATIVE ANTIBIOTIC DISC										
	OFX	AU	PEF	CTZ	CN	CPX	CEP	TRX	S	CEF	
18-30	3	3R	3R	3S	3S	3S	3R	3S	3S	3R	3R
31-40	5	5S	5R	5S	5R	5R	5S	5S	5R	5S	5S
41-50	0	NO <i>P. aeruginosa</i> ISOLATED									
51-60	4	4R	4S	4R	4R	4S	4S	4R	4R	4R	4R
61-70	3	3R	3S	3R	3R	3S	3R	3R	3R	3S	3R
71-80	0	NO <i>P. aeruginosa</i> ISOLATED									
Total	15										

KEY

OFX = Ofloxacin, AU = Augmentin, PEF = Peflacin, CTZ = Ceftazidime, CN = Gentamycin, CPX=Ciprofloxacin, CEP=Ceporex, TRX Ceftriaxone, S=Streptomycin, CEF=Cefuroxime.

R= Resistant

S= Sensitive

Discussion

The total number of subjects that were used in this research was 385 out of which 200 were males while 185 were females as compared to other studies recorded by [15] which had a total number of 100 patients enrolled in their study, out of which 62 were males while 38 were females. It has been noted in a study that enrolled 374 patients of which males are dominant 227 comparing counterpart female 147 patients. Out of the 385 subjects, 345 bacteria were isolated from their specimen. There were mixed growth in some specimen while there was no bacteria growth in some specimen. Out of the 345 isolates 188 (54.45%) Gram-negative bacteria were isolated [16]. This includes *Escherichia coli* 66 (35.1%), *Pseudomonas aerogenosa* 64(34.0%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* 29(15.4%) and *Proteus mirabilis* 29 (15.4%) both in diabetic and non diabetic male and female while 157(45.50%) Gram-positive bacteria were isolated both in diabetic and non diabetic male and female. The Gram positive bacteria isolated include *Staphylococcus aureus* 88 (56.0%), *Streptococcus pyogenes* 42 (27.0%) and *Bacillus anthracis* 27 (17.19%).

Similarly, in several recent studies, Gram –negative bacteria were the commonest agents as observed by [17] in Kuwait. It has been reported that gram negative bacilli comprised 51.2%, 76%, 76%, 57.6%, 51.4%, 52%, 67% of the total organisms which were isolated in different studies [18]. Our findings are also in line with [19] who reported that Gram-negative bacteria were the predominant pathogens constituting 83 (56.08%) of the isolates, while Gram-positive cocci were 41(27.7%), Gram – negative anaerobes 12(8.1%) and Candida species 12(8.1%).

In our finding, aerobic gram negative bacteria were the predominant pathogens constituting 188 (54.49%) while aerobic gram positive were 157 (44.7%) this is in line with previous studies by [20] which states that gram negative bacteria were predominant pathogens constituting 83(56.08%) of the isolate, while gram positive cocci were 41(27.7%).

Our findings in this research was in contrast with earlier studies by [21] who reported gram-positive bacteria mainly *Staphylococcus aureus* was the predominant pathogen, which comprised 57.2% and 73.6% of their isolates respectively. Therefore, there seems to be a changing trend in the organisms causing diabetic foot infections, with gram-negative bacteria replacing gram-positive bacteria as commonest agents. Thus, it may be essential to select antibiotics that are more effective against Gram-negative bacteria in contrast to Gram-positive organisms, which clinicians are inclined to. This difference could be explained by different types of infections as most mild infections are caused by aerobic Gram positive Cocci such as *S. aureus* and *Streptococci* while deeper limb threatening infections are usually polymicrobial and caused by Gram-positive cocci, gram negative bacilli and anaerobes. The gram positive organisms isolated in this research are *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pyogenes* and *Bacillus anthracis* while Gram negative bacteria are *Pseudomonas aerogenosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia* and *Proteus mirabilis*. They were seen in both diabetic and non diabetic male and female subjects.

In diabetic male group, the following bacteria were isolated and tested for antibiotic susceptibility: gram positive bacteria are *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pyogene* and *Bacillus anthracis* while Gram negative bacteria are *Pseudomonas aerogenosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia* and *Proteus mirabilis*.

Staphylococcus aureus in male 26 while female is 17, *Escherichia coli* in male subject is 20 while female subject were 15, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* male diabetic subjects 15 while female is 19, *Proteus mirabilis* male 9 female 5, *Streptococcus pyogenes* male 14, female 8, *Bacillus anthracis* male 7 female 10 and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* male 7 female 7. A total number of 31 samples showed no bacteria growth in both male and female while a total of 14 samples showed poly microbial growth. It was observed that the most common age presented with diabetic foot in this study was those in the ages between 51-60 years in the male group followed by those of the ages between 41-50 years and those in 18-30 has the lowest number. While the non diabetic female group between 31-40 years has the highest number and those in 41-50 and 51-60 has the same number of subjects. Those in the age groups 18-30 and 31-40 have the same number of subject and the lowest [7].

In the diabetic male group those in the age group 51-60 has the highest number followed by those of the age groups 41-50 and 61-70 years while 18-30 and 71-80 age groups had the lowest. Comparing with the non diabetic male group those in the age groups 31-40 and 51-60 had the highest number while those of the age group 71-80 years have the lowest. From this research it was observed that Ciprofloxacin had the highest sensitivity with four out of five age groups. Erythromycin and Streptomycin showed the highest resistance hence it was resistant to all the bacteria isolate that is four age groups out of five age groups. Bacteria isolate from age group 41-50 showed the highest resistance hence they were resistant to all of the ten antimicrobial used. There was no bacteria isolated from age group 61-70.

Looking at the bacteria isolates according to the two groups that were compared that is Diabetic and Non-Diabetic, the following observations were made a total number of *E. coli* 66 was isolated its distribution is: diabetic male 20 while diabetic female is 15, non-diabetic male is 14 while non-diabetic female is 17. Total: male 34 female 32. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*: diabetic male 15 while diabetic female is 19, non-diabetic male is 11 while non-diabetic female is 19. Total: male 26 female 38.

Staphylococcus aureus: diabetic male 26 while diabetic female is 17, non-diabetic male is 21 while non-diabetic female is 24. Total: male 47 female 41.

Klebsiella pneumoniae: diabetic male 7 while diabetic female is 7, non-diabetic male is 8 while non-diabetic female is 7. Total: male 15 female 14.

Proteus mirabilis: diabetic male 9 while diabetic female is 5, non-diabetic male is 7 while non-diabetic female is 8. Total: male 16 female 13.

Bacillus anthracis: diabetic male 7 while diabetic female is 10, non-diabetic male is 5 while non-diabetic female is 5. Total: male 12 female 15.

Streptococcus pyogenes: diabetic male 14 while diabetic female is 8, non-diabetic male is 9 while non-diabetic female is 11. Total: male 23 female 19.

The male group had the highest isolate of gram negative except *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* that were higher in the female group. In the gram positive bacteria male also dominated except *Bacillus anthracis* that was high in the female. *E. coli* is higher in the diabetic 35 while the non diabetic 31. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 34 while non diabetic 30. The presence of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Proteus* spp. and other aerobic gram negative bacilli in septic complication of infected diabetic feet have been reported in various studies [13].

S. aureus is higher in the non diabetic 45 than in diabetic which is 43 and is the highest isolates bacteria in this study. *S. aureus*, which is consistent with report from India. From the finding in this study, it showed that the rates of isolation of Gram-negative and Gram-positive were 56.6% and 43.4%, respectively. This was in agreement with studies done in Zaria, Nigeria, 55% and 44% respectively. *K. pneumoniae* is higher in the non diabetic 15 while the diabetic is 14. *Proteus mirabilis* is higher in the diabetic 15 while the diabetic is 14. *Bacillus anthracis* is higher in the diabetic 17 while the non diabetic is 10. *Streptococcus pyogenes* is higher in the diabetic 22 while the non diabetic 20.

In diabetic female group the most frequently isolated bacteria is Gram negative bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 19 followed by *Staphylococcus aureus* 17 which is Gram positive organism while in the non diabetic female group the most frequently isolated bacteria is Gram negative *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 19 followed by *Staphylococcus aureus* 17 and *Escherichia coli* 17 while the least isolated bacteria Gram negative bacteria in diabetic female group is *Proteus mirabilis* 5 and Gram positive organism is *Bacillus anthracis* 4 while in non diabetic female group *Klebsiella pneumoniae* 7 is the least Gram-negative bacteria isolated and gram positive is *Streptococcus Pyogenes* 8 and *Bacillus Anthracis* 8.

Staphylococcus aureus, *Escherichia Coli* and *P.aeruginosa* were the most prevalent bacterial agents isolated, which is in agreement with previous studies conducted by [17]. In Egypt *Proteus mirabilis* (16.8%) is the commonest isolate. In Saudi Arabia *P. aeruginosa* 15.6% (n=134) and in South America *Pseudomonas* spp. (18.8%) was the common isolate.

Commonly isolated Gram-negative bacteria were *E. coli* 66 followed by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 64 from this study while from previous studies carried out by [15] the most commonly isolated Gram negative bacteria were *Pseudomonas*

species (18.89%) followed by *Echerichia coli*, comparable with studies conducted [16] common Gram negative isolates were *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. It was reported that *P. aeruginosa* 24(24.7%) was the most common Gram negative isolate. In another studies carried out by [6] they observed that *P. mirabilis* was the commonest Gram-negative aetiological agent followed by *E. coli* and *Peudomonas* spp.

However, from this research the commonly isolated Gram positive bacteria is *Staphylococcus aureus* 88 followed by *Streptococcus* spp 42 while the lowest is *Bacillus anthracis* both in diabetic and non diabetic male and female subjects. The predominant isolate in the present study was found to be *S. aureus*, which was 34%; this finding was higher when compared with previous reports from Italy (28.2%) and Nigeria (25.1% and 25%). This study is in agreement with the studies of [14] in which *Staphylococcus* spp. was the predominant isolate 25.19%. This difference may be due to improved facilities of the hospital management from these countries and their infection prevention and control program. However, it is lower than reports in Nigeria (44%) and other parts of Ethiopia Dessie (41.6%), Bahir Dar (69.7%), and Gondar (65.5%).

From this study the second most prevalence bacteria is *Escharichia coli* 66 (19.15%) and *P. aerogenosa* 64(18.6%) and the lowest isolated gram negative bacteria were *Klebsiella* spp., 29 (8.4%) and *P. mirabilis* 29(8.4%) respectively. However, the prevalence observed in this study is lower than the findings that were done previously in Jimma (96.3%), Addis Ababa (86.2%), Nigeria (82.8%), and Pakistan (96.7%). This variation in the isolation rates of bacteria among different studies might be due to difference in the characteristics of the population, the geographical distribution, sample collection, processing, and diagnostic techniques used.

From our study, the age groups with the highest bacteria isolate were 51-60 (6) and 61-80 (6) while the lowest isolate is from the age group 18-30 (3) and 31-40 (2) in non diabetic while in diabetic female the age group with highest isolated 41-50 (7) followed 51-60 (6) the least isolated is 61-70 (3) and 71-80 (4) . This agrees with the studies carried out by [9] in their study it observed that maximum patients affected were under the age of 51-60. Female diabetic group age group 18-30 had the highest isolate both in gram positive and gram negative while age group 71-80 had the lowest bacteria isolate. The mostly sensitive gram positive antibiotics were Ciprofloxacin and Peflacin while less sensitive is Amoxil and most sensitive gram negative Ofloxacin this is not in agreement with the findings of [5] they reported that more than 50% of the gram negative isolates were depicted resistance against Ciprofloxacin, Gentamycin and Tetracycline. Most resistant gram negative antibiotic disc are Gentamycin, Augmentin, Ceftriazone and Streptomycin.

Antibiotic susceptibility of isolates to commonly used antibiotics, out of the 17 *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates strains from diabetic female group all (17, 100%) were sensitive to Ciprofoxacin, 15 (88.2%), Rifampicin, Ceftazidine 12 (70%), Azithromycin 12 (70%), 6 (35.2) Streptomycin, 10 (58.1) Cefuroxime, Gentamycin 4 (23.5%), Erythromycin 4 (23.5%), Amoxil 7(41.1) Levofloxacin 14(82.3%). While in Gram negative isolate, Ciprofloxacin also had the highest sensitivity both in diabetic and non diabetic, male and female and all the age groups. *P. areoginosa* and *K. pneumonia* showed the highest resistance to Peflacin, Streptomycin, Cefuroxime, Gentamycin and Augmentin, Ceftazidine and Ceporex respectively.

None of the isolate showed 100% susceptibility of any of the antibiotic tested in all the age groups and in diabetic and non-diabetic male and female subjects except *Staphylococcus aureus* in diabetic female group. The low susceptibility of isolates observed in this study agrees with the report of other scholars [18]. There were low level of susceptibility of isolates tested with Amoxil, Augmentin, Gentamycin, Strptomycin and Ceftriazone this may be attributed to the fact that they have been widely abused and are frequently implicated in self medication in Nigeria. It has also reported that high level of antibiotic abuse in Nigeria arising from self-medication which is associated with inadequate dosage, over use and failure to comply with treatment regimen. These antibiotics are being sold over the counter with or without prescription [7].

Ciprofloxacin was relatively sensitive for both Gram-positive and Gram-negative isolates in non diabetic female group and diabetic group followed by Azithromycin in Gram-positive while in Gram negative is and Peflacin. The most resistant in Gram negative is Gentamycin, Augmentin, Cefraizone and streptomycin and for gram positive is Amoxil. This is also seen in the report of [30] in which Gram positive bacteria were sensitive to Vancomycin while Imipenem and Amikacin had acceptable sensitivity against Gram-negative. Ciprofloxacin and meropenem found to be relatively more effective for *E coli*, and comparable findings were reported by [19] with Ciprofloxacin (78.3%) and meropenem (84.1%). *K. pneumoniae* was highly resistant to Ampicillin and Augmentin (88.9%) each, and it was 66.7% susceptible for Ciprofloxacin, Gentamycin, and Trimethoprim- Sulfamethoxazole.

Most of the gram-positive bacteria from non diabetic female group were resistant to Amoxil and Gentamycin followed by Streptomycin while most of the gram-negative bacteria *P. mirabilis* were resistant to Augment, Peflacin. *K. Pneumoniae* was resistant to Augmentin, Ceftazidine, Ceporex, Gentamycin and Cefuroxime and sensitive to Peflacin,

Ceftriazone. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were resistant to Peflacin, Streptomycin, Ceftazidime and Gentamycin and *E.coli* was resistant to Ofloxacin while Ciprofoxacin and Ceftazidime were the most sensitive. Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria isolates were highly sensitive to Ciprofloxacin followed by Ceftazidime, Cefuroxime and Erythromycin.

The majority of gram-negative bacteria were sensitive to Ceftazidime, Gentamycin (34, 50.0%) followed by Ceftriazone, (33, 48.5%), Streptomycin (32, 47.1%), *Pseudomonas spp* were resistant to Levofloxacin, 13 (52%), *Staphylococcus aureus* were resistant to Amoxil, 12 (48%), *Escheriacia coli* were resistant to Peflacine and 11 (44%), *Proteus mirabilis* were resistant to Ceporex. None of the *Klebsiella* isolates was resistant to Ceftriazone and Gentamycin. The present study demonstrated that amoxicillin was resistant to 83% of Gram-positives which was higher than a study done in Dessie reported as amoxicillin had the highest resistance rate 78.9%. *Staphylococcus aureus* showed the highest sensitivity rate to most of the antimicrobial agents tested, which is comparable to previous study done in Ethiopia by [20] and lower than a study done by [16] (86.2%). In addition, *S aureus* showed the least resistance to Ceftriazone, Rifampicin, and Ciprofloxacin, which is comparable to the findings by [21]. *P aeruginosa* had the highest resistant rate which is comparable to previous studies done in Ethiopia, 39.9% and 43.4%. In previous study, *P aeruginosa* showed high resistance to piperacillin (60%) and Gentamicin (56%), but another study reported 100% resistance for both drugs [22]. This may be due to massive use of antimicrobials in the area without prescription and as empirical treatment option by physicians or prolonged use of antibiotics may be responsible for the development of more resistant strains of the pathogens [23].

However, *P aeruginosa* showed lower rate of resistance to meropenem (12%) and ciprofloxacin (24%), and this result is consistent with the data obtained by [24]. The average resistance rate of *E coli* in this report was 59.2%, which was higher than results reported by other studies. The average resistance rate for this isolate was 60.6%, and it is higher than the results documented from previous studies by [25]. *Enterobacter* species showed 100% resistance to tetracycline, which is higher than studies done in Ethiopia and abroad. Most of gram-negative bacteria isolate showed high level of resistance to tested antibiotics. This might be due to these antibiotics are most commonly prescribed irrationally, which is in line with these studies.

Conclusion

From this research, it was observed that peripheral vascular disease (PVD) and neuropathy was significantly higher in the diabetic patients than in non diabetic patients. It was also observed that the male are more in number compared to female with non healing foot ulcer. The diabetic patients have a longer duration of stay in the hospital compared to non diabetics due to non healing ulcers. Aggressive treatment of infections, corrections of vascular occlusion diseases, adequate wound treatment and care and appropriate pressure mitigation were essential steps in treatment protocol. Health education to all patients with foot ulcers particularly in case of diabetic patients suffering from PVD and neuropathy is of essence.

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